

DEVELOPMENT OF PARKINSON DISEASE DETECTION SYSTEM USING CNN

Dr. B. Surekha Reddy
Assistant Professor,
Dept. of ECE
Institute of Aeronautical
Engineering
Hyderabad,India

M.Trisha
Dept.of ECE
Institute of Aeronautical
Engineering
Hyderabad,India

A.Yashashwini
Dept.of ECE
Institute of Aeronautical
Engineering
Hyderabad,India

V.Sumanth
Dept.of ECE
Institute of Aeronautical
Engineering
Hyderabad,India

Abstract— *Parkinson's Disease (PD) is a progressive central nervous system disorder that is caused due to the neural degeneration mainly in the substantia nigra in the brain. Tremors in hand is usually an initial symptom, followed by rigidity, bradykinesia, postural instability and impaired balance. In our proposed method, it presents a deep learning approach for classifying hand drawn images to detect parkinson's disease using Convolution neural network. We have used PNG format-based images for training and testing dataset which is available by Kaggle. We have applied CNN model, utilizing transfer learning with the pre-trained VGG16 architecture to classify Parkinson's disease using hand-drawn spiral and wave images. The model is initially trained with frozen base layers, followed by fine-tuning of the last few layers to improve accuracy. VGG16 is one of the best models and we have achieved 97% of training accuracy and 93% of testing accuracy for wave images and 98% of training accuracy and 86.67% of testing accuracy for spiral images respectively, it is comparatively more efficient than most existing methods.*

Keywords— *CNN, Deep learning, VGG16, Parkinson Disease, .PNG, spiral and wave images.*

I. INTRODUCTION

Parkinson's disease (PD) is a neurodegenerative condition marked by stiffness, bradykinesia, and tremors in the motor system. It manifests as the death of dopaminergic neurons in the substantia nigra parts compacta within the midbrain[1]The best chance of receiving treatment and delaying the course of Parkinson's disease is early identification. Due to their reliance on subjective evaluations and clinical assessment, traditional techniques of detecting Parkinson's disease (PD) might cause delays in diagnosis. Consequently, there's been an increasing amount of interest in using deep learning and machine learning approaches to help with early detection, especially when it comes to the interpretation of medical pictures.

Because deep learning, and more specifically convolutional neural networks (CNNs), can learn hierarchical representations of data, they have demonstrated impressive performance in medical picture classification tasks [2]. Transfer learning techniques have made heavy use of pre-trained CNNs, including VGG16,

which enable models to leverage massive amounts of past knowledge gleaned from massive datasets like ImageNet [3]. Numerous medical image analysis tasks, such as organ segmentation, tumour identification, and disease classification, have been tackled by these architectures [4].

In this paper, we employ VGG16 as the base model for detecting Parkinson's disease from spiral and wave images. These images, derived from drawing tests, serve as a non-invasive diagnostic tool to assess motor function impairment associated with Parkinson's disease [5]. By fine-tuning the VGG16 model and introducing custom fully connected layers, we aim to improve classification accuracy and provide a robust tool for PD detection. The proposed method involves freezing the base layers of VGG16 to retain its pre-trained features, followed by the unfreezing of certain layers for fine-tuning, thus enhancing its performance on the specific task of Parkinson's disease classification.

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

Numerous investigations have looked into the use of deep learning methods for the early diagnosis of Parkinson's disease (PD), specifically by analysing motor deficits recorded by handwriting and drawing activities.

Moetesum et al. [6] recently presented an automatic hand-drawn spiral picture method for Parkinson's disease (PD) identification. The system used a Support Vector Machine (SVM) for classification and a CNN for feature extraction. There were 75 subjects in the evaluation dataset, 38 of whom were healthy and 37 of whom were Parkinson's disease patients. The outcomes of the trial showed that the system's highest accuracy was 83%. Even though the system performed better than its competitors, more development is still needed because the results are still not entirely satisfying. Furthermore, the system's performance was assessed solely based on accuracy, precision, and recall; other, more thorough metrics like F1-score were not taken into account..

Using hand-drawn spiral images, Akter et al. [7] examined how well various categorisation methods performed in identifying Parkinson's disease (PD).

Among the classification methods that were looked at were K-Nearest Neighbour (KNN), Decision Tree (DT), Gradient Boosting (GB), and Random Forest (RF). The authors also used the Histogram of Orientated Gradients (HOG) technique to collect features, which they then fed into each classifier separately. A total of 102 spiral image samples—51 from PD patients and 51 from healthy subjects—were used for the examination. According to the trial data, the KNN approach had the highest accuracy, coming in at 89.33%. Even though KNN performed better than the other classifiers, the outcomes are still not ideal and need to be improved. Furthermore, the evaluation ignored other crucial metrics like the F1-score and AUC that could offer a more thorough insight of the model's performance in favour of focussing only on specificity, sensitivity, and accuracy.

In summary, existing research underscores the effectiveness of CNNs in detecting Parkinson's disease (PD) from spiral images, but several challenges remain. These include the need for large, labeled datasets, model complexity, and computational resource requirements. This paper builds upon previous work by proposing a VGG16-based approach, leveraging transfer learning to address these limitations. The focus is on achieving high diagnostic accuracy while maintaining model simplicity and reducing the need for extensive data by utilizing pre-trained weights and fine-tuning specific layers.

III. PROPOSED METHOD

A pre-trained VGG16 convolutional neural network (CNN) serves as the foundation model for feature extraction in the suggested method for diagnosing Parkinson's disease (PD). Custom dense layers are then used for binary classification. This method's main goal is to accurately categorise hand-drawn spiral and wave images into either the PD or healthy categories while minimising overfitting and guaranteeing maximum computing efficiency. The block diagram to identify the PD is displayed in Figure 1.

Figure.1 The proposed approach blockdiagram for detection

The dataset comprises of hand-drawn spiral and wave images divided into two classifications (PD and Healthy), which is derived from [8]. The dataset is divided into two main categories, as seen in fig. 2: samples from patients with Parkinson's disease are included in the first category, while samples from healthy persons (i.e., those not afflicted by the condition) are included in the second category. The dataset consists of 102 hand-drawn wave images and 102 hand-drawn spiral images, of which 51 samples fall into the category of Parkinson's disease and 51 samples fall into the category of healthy.

Category	No. of samples	Samples of the hand-draw wave images
Parkinson	51	
Healthy	51	

Category	No. of samples	Samples of the hand-draw spiral images
Parkinson	51	
Healthy	51	

Figure 2 . Dataset Preparation

The well-known CNN model VGG-16 architecture, which is seen in Figure 3, has proven to perform exceptionally well in image classification tasks. There are three fully connected layers and thirteen convolutional layers totalling 16 layers. The model learns complex features at several levels of abstraction by employing small 3x3 convolutional filters with a stride of 1, as shown in Figure. Max pooling layers down sample the feature maps while extracting the most notable features, using a 2x2 filter size and a stride of 2. Using a smaller dataset, these feature extraction layers can be optimised for domain-specific applications, like hand-drawn spiral or wave images for Parkinson's disease identification. This customization of VGG-16 creates a robust framework for automatically extracting discriminative features, enhancing its effectiveness in medical image analysis.

Figure3 Architecture of VGG16

IV. IMPLEMENTATION

TensorFlow and Keras in Python were used to build the suggested system, which uses hand-drawn spiral and wave images to diagnose Parkinson's disease (PD). The VGG16 model was pre-trained on the ImageNet dataset. Using transfer learning, the VGG16 architecture was used as a feature extractor. To normalise the image data, we used Keras' Image Data Generator class. Every image in the dataset was scaled to fall between [0, 1] and shrunk to 256x256 pixels. The training and testing sets of the dataset were loaded from the corresponding directories.

We used the VGG16 model pre-trained on the ImageNet dataset, omitting the top fully connected layers, for feature extraction. To apply transfer learning, the pre-trained weights were maintained by freezing the VGG16 convolutional base layers. A number of fully connected layers with batch normalization and dropout were constructed on top of the VGG16 basic model to solve the binary classification task (PD vs. healthy). The convolutional base's output was compressed into a single-dimensional vector. of ReLU activation functions, three dense layers of 256, 128 and 64 units, respectively, were introduced. After every dense layer, batch normalisation and dropout (with a dropout rate of 0.5) were employed to increase training stability and avoid overfitting. A sigmoid activation function and single

neuron final output layer used for classification of binary.

Layer (type)	Output Shape	Param #
vgg16 (Functional)	(None, 8, 8, 512)	14,714,688
flatten_1 (Flatten)	(None, 32768)	0
dense_4 (Dense)	(None, 256)	8,388,864
batch_normalization_3 (BatchNormalization)	(None, 256)	1,024
dropout_3 (Dropout)	(None, 256)	0
dense_5 (Dense)	(None, 128)	32,896
batch_normalization_4 (BatchNormalization)	(None, 128)	512
dropout_4 (Dropout)	(None, 128)	0
dense_6 (Dense)	(None, 64)	8,256
batch_normalization_5 (BatchNormalization)	(None, 64)	256
dropout_5 (Dropout)	(None, 64)	0
dense_7 (Dense)	(None, 1)	65

Model: "sequential_1"

Total params: 23,146,561 (88.30 MB)
 Trainable params: 8,430,977 (32.16 MB)
 Non-trainable params: 14,715,584 (56.14 MB)
 Found 72 images belonging to 2 classes.
 Found 30 images belonging to 2 classes.

The model is trained for 10 epochs on the enlarged training dataset with the Adam optimiser and a learning rate of 0.001. After initial training, fine-tuning is performed by unfreezing the VGG16 model's last four convolutional layers, allowing the pre-trained layers to adjust to the unique properties of the hand-drawn spiral images. The learning rate is set to 0.0001 to ensure gradual weight updates during fine-tuning.

Following training and fine-tuning, the model was tested on the test dataset to determine its performance. Accuracy was the major metric used. In addition, we created a confusion matrix and classification report to evaluate the model's capacity to correctly distinguish PD patients and healthy persons.

V. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Spiral images

After training the model for 10 epochs and then fine-tuning for another 10 epochs, the final accuracy on the training dataset ranged from 87% to 98%, while the testing dataset achieved 86%, as shown in fig4.

Figure4 Training and Testing accuracy of spiral images.

After training the suggested model, we evaluate it by providing test data as input and determining if the given spiral image represents a Parkinson's patient or a healthy individual. The suggested method first determines the label heading and then predicts whether the image is healthy or Parkinson's. Figure 5 displays the prediction of images.

Figure5 Testing using spiral images.

In fig6 ,the confusion matrix below provides further insight into the model's predictions. It shows that out of 15 healthy images 14 images were predicted as healthy images and 1 image was predicted falsely. And out of 15 parkinson images 12 images were predicted as Parkinson disease image and 3 images were predicted falsely.

Figure6 Confusion matrix for detection of Parkinson disease and healthy.

Figure 7 shows the precision, recall, and F1-scores for each class (Healthy and Parkinson's). The Parkinson's class had somewhat higher precision and recall than the Healthy class, indicating that the model was more effective at diagnosing PD than identifying healthy individuals.

```

2/2 27s 13s/step
[[14  1]
 [ 3 12]]
precision recall f1-score support
0      0.82    0.93    0.87    15
1      0.92    0.80    0.86    15
accuracy          0.87    30
macro avg         0.87    0.87    0.87    30
weighted avg      0.87    0.87    0.87    30
    
```

Figure 7. Classification report.

B. Wave images

And for wave images , the training dataset accuracy reached approximately from 87% to 97% and testing dataset accuracy reached to 93% shown in fig8.

Figure 8 Training and Testing of wave images.

After training the suggested model, we test it by passing the test data as input and determining if the wave image represents a Parkinson's patient or a healthy individual. The suggested method assigns a label heading to the image and predicts whether it is healthy or Parkinson's. Figure 9 shows the prediction of images.

Figure 9. Testing using wave images.

In fig10 ,the confusion matrix below provides further insight into the model’s predictions. It shows that out of 15 healthy images 14 images were predicted as healthy images and 1 image was predicted falsely. And out of 15

parkinson images 14 images were predicted as Parkinson disease image and 1 image was predicted falsely.

Figure 10. Confusion matrix for detection of Parkinson disease and healthy (wave images).

The complete classification report (fig11) shows the precision, recall, and F1-score for each class (Healthy and Parkinson's). The Parkinson's class had the same precision, recall, and F1 score, indicating that the model was comparable in detecting PD and healthy persons.

Figure 11. Classification report.

Compared to previous studies, such as those by Moetesum et al. and Akter et al., which achieved accuracy rates between 83% and 89%, the proposed VGG16-based model demonstrated superior performance, achieving a 93% test accuracy for wave images and 86% for spiral images. This improvement can be attributed to the advanced feature extraction capabilities of the VGG16 architecture and the effectiveness of transfer learning.

Hand draw spiral images

Method	Accuracy
AlexNet [9]	92.16%
Fine-tuned VGG-19 [10]	88.50%
HOG-CNN [11]	84.00%
Proposed Method	98.00%

Table1: Comparison with previous methods using spiral images.

Hand draw wave images

Method	Accuracy
RF in [12]	84.67%
Fine-tuned VGG19 [10]	88.00%
Resnet 34[13]	83.33%
Proposed Method	97.00%

Table2: Comparison with previous methods using wave images

VI. CONCLUSION

In this study, we suggested a VGG16-based convolutional neural network (CNN) for detecting Parkinson's disease (PD) using hand-drawn spiral and wave images. Using transfer learning and fine-tuning methodologies, we achieved 97% and 98% accuracy for the wave and spiral picture datasets, respectively. In contrast to prior studies that used typical machine learning approaches, our approach greatly enhanced accuracy while preserving a basic, effective model architecture. The proposed approach may aid in the early diagnosis of Parkinson's disease. To improve the model's performance and ensure that it works on a variety of datasets, actual clinical photos are necessary. Future study will concentrate on applying the model to a larger dataset containing more image samples. Future research may investigate the use of different machine learning algorithms for Parkinson's disease identification..

VII. REFERENCES

- [1] Timothy J. Wroge; Yasin Özkanca; Cenk Demiroglu; Dong Si; David C. Atkins; Reza Hosseini Ghomi, "Parkinson's Disease Diagnosis Using Machine Learning"
- [2] Y. LeCun, Y. Bengio, and G. Hinton, "Deep learning," *Nature*, vol. 521, no. 7553, pp. 436-444, 2015.
- [3] K. Simonyan and A. Zisserman, "Very deep convolutional networks for large-scale image recognition," *arXiv preprint arXiv:1409.1556*, 2014.
- [4] G. Litjens et al., "A survey on deep learning in medical image analysis," *Medical Image Analysis*, vol. 42, pp. 60-88, 2017.
- [5] I. Salhi et al., "Handwriting in Parkinson's disease: a marker of diagnosis and severity," *Journal of Neurology*, vol. 256, no. 1, pp. 183-190, 2009.
- [6] M. Moetesum, M. S. Sarfraz, and M. A. Malik, "Automatic Parkinson's disease detection using hand-drawn spiral images," *Proc. IEEE Int. Conf. on Innovations in Information Technology (IIT)*, pp. 99-104, 2019.
- [7] S. Akter, K. M. A. Hasan, S. Ahmed, and M. T. Islam, "Comparative analysis of different classification techniques for detecting Parkinson's disease from spiral drawings," *Proc. IEEE Region 10 Conference (TENCON)*, pp. 234-239, 2020.
- [8] Zham P, Kumar DK, Dabnichki P, Poosapadi Arjunan S and Raghav S (2017) Distinguishing Different Stages of Parkinson's Disease Using Composite Index of Speed and Pen-Pressure of Sketching a Spiral. *Front. Neurol.* 8:435. doi: 10.3389/fneur.2017.00435
- [9] I. Razzak, I. Kamran, and S. Naz, "Deep analysis of handwritten notes for early diagnosis of neurological disorders," in *2020 International Joint Conference on Neural Networks (IJCNN)*, 2020: IEEE, pp. 1-6, doi: 10.1109/IJCNN48605.2020.9207087.
- [10] M. Shaban, "Deep convolutional neural network for Parkinson's disease based handwriting screening," in *2020 IEEE 17th International Symposium on Biomedical Imaging Workshops (ISBI Workshops)*, 2020: IEEE, pp. 1-4, doi: 10.1109/ISBIWorkshops50223.2020.9153407.
- [11] M. Aghzal and A. Mourhir, "Early diagnosis of Parkinson's disease based on handwritten patterns using deep learning," in *2020 Fourth International Conference on Intelligent Computing in Data Sciences (ICDS)*, 2020: IEEE, pp. 1-6, doi: 10.1109/ICDS50568.2020.9268738.
- [12] M. I. Shaik, B. Ranjitha, and P. Renjith, "Spotting Parkinson's disorder with OpenCV, and the Helix/Wave using random forest classifier," *Materials Today: Proceedings*, 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.matpr.2021.03.343.
- [13] A. B. Muralikrishna, "Efficient detection of parkinson disease using multiple machine learning techniques," *Masters thesis, Dublin, National College of Ireland*, 2020.